

Kissabekov Almas

specialist degree, Kazakh Academy of Transport and Communications named
M. Tynyshpayev
Kazakhstan, Almaty

THE ROLE OF EXPERT AUTHOR AND TECHNICAL SUPERVISION IN ENSURING COMPLIANCE WITH CONSTRUCTION NORMS AND STANDARDS AT ALL STAGES OF PROJECT IMPLEMENTATION

Abstract: The article examines the significance of expert author and technical supervision in construction projects. It analyzes their functions, differences, and impact on construction quality. Special attention is given to compliance control with construction norms and standards, risk minimization, and defect prevention at all stages of project implementation. The article describes methods of interaction between supervisory bodies, designers, and contractors. Approaches to assessing the effectiveness of supervisory activities and their impact on compliance with construction requirements are examined. Key factors influencing the effectiveness of supervisory activities and methods for their optimization within construction projects are also examined.

Keywords: construction supervision, technical control, construction quality, standards, risks, automation.

INTRODUCTION

Construction is one of the most regulated areas of activity. In it, following the norms and standards that guarantee the level of safety, durability, and operational reliability of the facility, as well as compliance with project solutions, are especially important. Yet, practice shows that defects in construction and discrepancies in design solutions are an urgent problem. This could be related both to the human factor and shortcomings in the organization of control at various stages of construction.

To minimize risks that concern the non-conformity of building codes, mechanisms of author's and technical supervision are used. Author's supervision, which is carried out by the designer, provides for checking how much the work executed corresponds to the design documentation, while technical supervision carried out by specialized services or the customer provides for quality control of construction

processes and materials. Though highly spread, however, the very effectiveness of this tool application still remains a debating point from scientific and practical viewpoints.

The objective of this work is to analyze the role of author's and technical supervision in securing the observance of regulatory requirements for construction projects. The article examines theoretical positions about the content of supervision activities, the legal basis for their implementation, and methods for assessing effectiveness.

MAIN PART. THEORETICAL ASPECTS OF AUTHOR'S AND TECHNICAL SUPERVISION

In the process of building facilities for different purposes, control of observance of regulatory requirements is provided by author's and technical supervision, which, though having similar goals, perform different functions.

Author's supervision is the activity of a design organization or architect directed at ensuring that the construction work has been carried out in compliance with the approved design documentation. Author's supervision starts with the beginning of construction works and is regulated by legislative acts. The main tasks of the author's supervision include observance of correspondence to the designed decisions, changes in the documentation if needed, and detention of deviations from the approved norms. The effectiveness of author's supervision is largely dependent on the competence of designers and their interaction with construction organizations [1].

In its turn, **technical supervision** provides for functions of control regarding construction quality, correspondence of materials to standards and regulatory documents requirements, as well as observance of construction technologies. This kind of supervision is provided by a customer or special independent organizations responsible for construction process monitoring. Technical supervision in a number of countries, including the USA, is a mandatory component of construction control, and its absence may result in legal sanctions [2].

Both types of supervision are of key importance at different stages of the life cycle of a facility. Author's supervision prevents structural and architectural errors during the construction stage of a building, while technical supervision ensures that the work

performed meets the established requirements. Research shows that without effective technical supervision, construction defects often lead to costly rework. In the USA, where annual construction spending reaches \$1,3 trillion, rework accounts for approximately 5% of this amount, costing the industry over \$65 billion each year [3].

Thus, the integrated use of author's and technical supervision reduces the likelihood of construction defects, promotes the rational use of resources and ensures compliance with building codes, which ultimately affects the safety and durability of structures.

REGULATORY AND LEGAL FRAMEWORK FOR CONSTRUCTION SUPERVISION

The regulatory framework for construction supervision is the legislative, state standard, and technical regulation acts that regulate activities in construction. For example, in Kazakhstan, a central document that outlines the requirements for construction is the **Urban Development Code of the Republic of Kazakhstan**, which regulates issues of designing, construction, reconstruction, and major repairs of facilities, and establishment of binding standards of safety and quality [4].

In general, the main division of regulatory acts is presented by general construction standards, for example, **International Building Code (IBC)**, and specialized standards that regulate particular types of works. Their task is to ensure the safety of facilities and their correspondence to modern requirements. To effectively control their compliance, the **Technical Regulation for Construction Products** was developed in Kazakhstan, which regulates the requirements at the stages of design, execution, and acceptance of construction works.

In the USA, construction supervision is regulated by a combination of federal, state, and local laws, with key oversight provided by agencies such as the **Occupational Safety and Health Administration (OSHA)** and the **International Code Council (ICC)**. One of the fundamental regulatory documents is the **IBC**, which establishes safety, structural, and fire protection standards for buildings across the country. Additionally, the **Code of Federal Regulations (CFR)**, particularly **Title 29**, governs workplace safety and construction site regulations under OSHA's

authority. At the state level, building codes are often based on IBC provisions but may include additional requirements tailored to local conditions.

Self-regulatory organizations (SRO) form a significant part of the industry's legal setup, standing between government agencies and private construction companies. Such organizations in the USA, like the **American Institute of Architects (AIA)**, play an important role in maintaining high construction standards and ensuring the quality of design solutions.

METHODS FOR ASSESSING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF SUPERVISORY MEASURES

Evaluation of the effectiveness of author's and technical supervision is a key stage for ensuring high quality of construction projects and compliance with all norms and standards. Modern approaches to this evaluation include both quantitative and qualitative methods that allow for an accurate determination of the impact of supervision on the construction result.

One of the key methods for assessing the effectiveness of author's and technical supervision is the analysis of defects and deviations in the construction process. This method allows us to identify how effectively the control functions, and also determines opportunities for improving the construction process (table 1).

Table 1. Causes of building defects through the lifecycle of building [5]

Design stage	Construction stage	Curing stage	O&M (Operation and Maintenance) stage
Design errors, selection of inappropriate materials and methods, no consideration of constructability, insufficient design documents.	Lack of material performance, poor supervision and inspection, omission of product parts, poor workmanship, non-compliance with specifications.	Poor temperature and humidity control, no curing material followed, damage caused by other work, insufficient curing time.	Poor O&M, O&M errors or mistakes, no regular inspection, damage due to natural disasters, etc., careless use of residents.
Lack of integrated communication among project participants; lack of integrated project quality management; Frequent change orders of project owners.			
Before service			After service

Key indicators in this context include the **number and types of violations** identified during various control activities, such as compliance checks with building codes, standards, and design documentation. These violations can stem from different risk sources in the construction industry, ranging from minor non-compliances to critical errors that impact the functionality and safety of a facility. Figure 1 illustrates the main sources of risks in construction.

Figure 1. Sources of risks in construction [6]

Another important method is the **assessment of compliance with construction deadlines**. The effectiveness of supervision in this context can be measured by deviations from the planned completion dates of work stages. In practice, projects with stricter control comply with deadlines more often than those where supervision is limited to author's checks only [7]. This is due to the fact that technical supervision allows for the prompt identification and elimination of problems that may affect the timing of work.

Quality of building materials used in construction sites can also indicate good supervision. Through standardization methods to **check on the materials** while carrying out supervisory roles helps cut down numbers of poor qualities materials on site during and after project implementation. For instance, in the USA, the practice of regular inspection of materials at all stages of construction enables them to minimize the probability of the usage of non-standard materials. The given indicator is very often applied in order to assess the effectiveness of supervision, since the incompliance of materials with standards may further on result in defects in the facility operation.

Furthermore, the intensive use of data analysis tools, such as **Building Information Modeling (BIM)** and automated monitoring systems, enables real-time

assessment of supervision effectiveness and ensures compliance with all standards and building regulations. Such systems will not only reveal violations but also prevent them due to notifications of deviations far in advance.

The assessment of the effectiveness of supervisory measures is a complex and multicomponent process. Such an approach enables to create a more objective view about the condition of construction and to increase the quality of objects.

RISKS AND LIMITATIONS OF AUTHOR'S AND TECHNICAL SUPERVISION

Despite the importance of author's and technical supervision for ensuring construction quality, there are a number of risks and limitations that can significantly reduce their effectiveness. These factors can be both external and internal, and it is important to take them into account when organizing control over the construction process.

One of the main risks is the **human factor**. Errors made both during the design process and during supervision activities can lead to serious consequences for the safety and durability of the facility. For example, author supervision can be limited by insufficient qualifications or overload of designers, which reduces its effectiveness in real time. In a number of cases the discrepancy between design solutions and current building codes is a consequence of errors at the design stage that were not promptly detected during supervision.

Another important **limitation is the lack of funding and resources**. In some cases, author's and technical supervision cannot be fully implemented due to budget constraints. For example, a reduction in the number of inspections or insufficient frequency of checks can lead to an increase in the number of defects at later stages of construction.

In addition, there are **legal and organizational constraints**. In some countries problems with the effectiveness of supervision arise from insufficient coordination between various public and private bodies. This leads to duplication of efforts, as well as insufficient control over compliance with building codes at all levels. Inconsistency

in requirements and the lack of clear regulation of supervision functions between different agencies increases the likelihood that some violations will remain unnoticed.

It is also worth noticing such a factor as technology. In the context of new technologies application for construction, for example, BIM and automatic monitoring systems, the **risk of non-conformity of new technologies standards** can appear [8]. Sometimes it is not possible to quickly adapt existing norms and rules to new technological solutions; as the result, technical and legal gaps in supervision process may appear.

Therefore, authors' and technical risks and limits need weighing and elaboration of the effective mechanisms of their limitation. It is crucial in this context that such supervision should not only be systemic and comprehensive but also flexible enough to respond promptly to changes both in the construction industry in general and to consider all possible risk factors.

CONCLUSION

Author and technical supervision play a crucial role in ensuring that buildings comply with construction codes and contribute significantly to achieving the highest levels of safety and durability. Effectiveness of such supervision depends on the one hand on a qualification of the specialists, existence of proper conditions, and good coordination between a variety of processes participants. Apart from the fact that qualitative construction is stimulated by the nature of the regulatory framework and methodologies for assessing effectiveness of supervision, there are also a number of risks and limitations related to human factor, organizational and legal and technological problems. The integrated control systems for such risks should be implemented and continuously updated with regulations and newly developed technological solutions; in the future, this will enhance the efficiency of construction supervision and observance of all standards at every stage of the project implementation process.

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